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a peer review system is another uphill task due to shortcomings in scientific manpower, infrastructure, and other problems like language, finance and professional publication. Discussions on these issues with the colleagues from the peer journals faced with the same obstacles would surely help pave the ground to promote the much needed success of such journals.

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ABSTRACT NO. 24 The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine: An Emerging International Iraqi Peer-Reviewed Medical Journal

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There has been a tremendous need for an independent peer-reviewed medical journal which aims at the advancement of medical knowledge rather than promotion in this country.

Journal foundation: From the first beginning of this journal in 2005 as Al Karkh Journal of Medicine, the decision was made that the journal should adhere to the internationally accepted standards of modern peer-reviewed medical journals. All the editorial policies were adapted from the policies of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), World Association of Medical Editors (WAME), and the Committee on publication ethics (COPE). From the third issue of December 2005 the journal has become The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine the official peer-reviewed medical journal of the Iraqi ministry of health.

Aims: Initially, the primary goal of the Journal was to publish research work confined to Iraq, which were of importance for both local and international readers. Another aim was to make the research work easily available for international readers thus a sincere attempt is being made to disseminate the medical knowledge to all medical fraternity of the world.

International journal: From September 2007 issue of the journal, various editors from all parts of the world joined our journal. Now we have editors from 4 major continents in the world. In addition we have an International Editorial Board International editors including editorial board have the privileges of the Editor in Chief, as they can receive, evaluate manuscripts and provide the journal with an editorial decision. Until now the journal has been successful in publishing papers in more than 15 areas and disciplines of medicine. Authors located in Iraq, USA, India, Malaysia, Jordan, Malawi, and Zambia has contributed to the journal.

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ABSTRACT NO. 25 Weighted Impact Factor: A New Scientometrics Index

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The impact factor of a journal reflects the frequency with which the journal's articles are cited. It is the best available measure of journal quality. For calculation of impact factor, we just count the number of citations, no matter how prestigious the citing journal is. We think that impact factor as a measure of journal quality, may be improved if in its calculation, we not only take into account the number of citations, but also incorporate a factor reflecting the prestige of the citing journals relative to the cited journal. In calculation of this proposed "weighted impact factor," each citation has a coefficient (weight) the value of which is 1 if the citing journal is as prestigious as the cited journal; is $\uparrow 1$ if the citing journal is more prestigious than the cited journal; and is $\downarrow 1$ if the citing journal has a lower standing than the cited journal. In this way, journals receiving many citations from prestigious journals are considered prestigious themselves and those cited by low-status journals seek little credit. By considering both the number of citations and the prestige of the citing journals, we expect the weighted impact factor be a better scientometrics measure of journal quality.

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